

Zori Tex

Reducing the environmental
impact of the fashion industry

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BridgeAI

CASE STUDY

zori tex

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Reducing the environmental impact of the fashion industry

The fashion industry is hugely resource intensive. While estimates vary, it is thought the sector contributes at least 4% of global greenhouse gas emissions.

To compound matters, efforts to recycle clothing are hampered by the difficulty of accurately identifying fibre composition: more than 40% of garments are thought to be incorrectly labelled, and traditional manual or laboratory-based methods of classifying and sorting are either too time-consuming or economically unviable. Only around 1% of the millions of tonnes of clothing that make it to the market each year are recycled into new clothing – the rest goes to landfill or incineration.

Zori Tex, a startup founded in 2022 by former fashion and textiles leader Alexandra Harrod, is using cutting-edge machine vision and AI techniques – and deep sector knowledge – to optimise the sorting of used textiles, enabling old, worn-out clothing to be turned into new, usable materials at scale.

“Textile waste is complex. It’s made of many different fibres and blends, some at very low percentages, and there are lots of contaminants. It’s hard to identify and segregate individual fibres, which is key to ensuring productive and efficient recycling. This is a wicked problem but a really important one.”

Alexandra Harrod
CEO, Zori Tex

Zori Tex’s textile analysis system uses an infrared hyperspectral camera to measure the absorbance and reflection of light within certain wavelengths. The company’s bespoke machine learning algorithm then delves into its extensive training to identify the composition of fibres – at better-than-human performance – readying the materials for fibre-to-fibre recycling.

Building a robust algorithm from the ground up

“The problem we’re trying to solve at Zori Tex lends itself very well to deep learning approaches. But because we’re among the first to tackle this and the datasets and hardware are relatively novel, we can’t just take an off-the-shelf algorithm and put it to work – we are building from scratch. We approached BridgeAI to make sure we are utilising the most up-to-date techniques and can speak to experts who will challenge us and give us ideas about where we can improve our model.”

Dominic Waithe

Lead Engineer, Zori Tex

The team at Zori Tex has been working with Dr Andy Corbett, Independent Scientific Advisor at The Alan Turing Institute, in partnership with BridgeAI. The programme supports SMEs in adopting AI into their businesses and products, and the Zori Tex team meets with Andy regularly to review and workshop developments around its technology. One of Andy’s key contributions has been the introduction of an approach that helps Zori Tex to interrogate and better understand the workings of its AI model, helping not only to validate the model but to provide important insights for optimisation.

“Andy thought it was a good idea to try this technique, but we were both surprised at how well it worked in practice. That has been one of the best things about this collaboration – when it results in something considerably more than the sum of its parts.”

Dominic Waithe

Lead Engineer, Zori Tex

Through BridgeAI, Zori Tex also received an Innovation Voucher at The Hartree Centre, valued at £15,000, to help optimise the accuracy of its machine learning model – particularly in identifying low-percentage fibres in textile compositions. The Hartree Centre’s team of scientists analysed Zori Tex’s data processing and AI systems, offering improvements using open-source tools and introducing new methods including statistical techniques to push performance and cut the model’s training time. As a result, Zori Tex and The Hartree Centre are continuing this work and collaborating on a further funding bid.

“Zori Tex is a model example of taking an innovative AI approach to solve an industrial problem that could otherwise not have been solved. Their product has the potential to be of great environmental importance and brings significant gains in manufacturing productivity and efficiency – all fuelled by turning an AI-based solution into a practical tool.”

Dr. Andrew Corbett

Independent Scientific Advisor for BridgeAI

Refining the model for maximum impact

Following a small industrial pilot at the end of 2024, the Zori Tex team is now working hard to hit the milestones that will allow it to deploy commercially. The company is also looking to open a funding round in 2025 to help finance its research, development and launch.

In particular, Zori Tex is looking to continue to improve the accuracy of its machine learning model and thus maximise the product's impact.

“There’s a lot of support available for startups in areas such as marketing, pitching and business development, but help to get under the bonnet and go deep into the technology is much harder to find. We look out for any potential support from BridgeAI because we know how valuable it can be towards our ambitions for developing our AI.”

Alexandra Harrod
CEO, Zori Tex

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